

ALGEBRAS OF FILTERS ON FINITE POSETS: INCIDENCE ALGEBRAS, GROUPS OF UNITS, HOMOLOGICAL INVARIANTS, AND HOPF ALGEBRA STRUCTURES

ALEXANDRO OLIVARES ACOSTA

ABSTRACT. We develop a systematic theory of the algebra of filters $\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ on a finite poset (\mathcal{X}, \preceq) over a commutative ring K .

Structure and embedding. The multiplication is defined via ideal-filter decompositions. We show that Butcher’s algebra on finite labeled forests is a special case. Thus $\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ extends the forest construction to arbitrary finite posets and retains its links with numerical integration and the Connes–Kreimer Hopf algebra. We construct an injective K -algebra homomorphism $\varphi: \mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, K) \hookrightarrow \mathbf{IA}(2^{\mathcal{X}}, \subseteq)$ into the Rota incidence algebra of the Boolean lattice, and show that when \mathcal{X} is an antichain, $\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, \mathbb{C})$ is isomorphic to the ring of arithmetical functions under unitary convolution.

Group of units. We study the group of units $\mathrm{GL}(\mathcal{X}, K) = \mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, K)^{\times}$. We prove $\mathrm{GL}(\mathcal{X}, K) \cong \mathrm{Un}(K) \times \mathrm{SL}(\mathcal{X}, K)$, where $\mathrm{SL}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ consists of elements with augmentation 1. Every element of $\mathrm{SL}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ admits a unique factorization as a product of elementary invertible functions, $\mathrm{SL}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ is nilpotent of class at most $|\mathcal{X}|$, and we give explicit finite presentations over \mathbb{Z} and finite cyclic rings.

Homological invariants. We show the defining relations of $\mathbf{AFF}(\mathcal{X})$ form a quadratic Gröbner basis, so $\mathbf{AF}_{\bullet}(\mathcal{X}, \mathbb{F})$ is Koszul for any field \mathbb{F} . We introduce the class of SU algebras, prove it is closed under quadratic duality, and show $\mathbf{AF}_{\bullet}(\mathcal{X})$ is a strictly stronger poset invariant than the Stanley–Reisner ring. We construct a minimal free biresolution, compute the Poincaré series, and determine the invariant ideals. Using the biresolution we compute the Hochschild (co)homology, identify the Ext algebra with the Koszul dual, and characterize the center $Z(\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X})) = \mathrm{HH}^0(\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}), \mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}))$ combinatorially.

Hopf algebra structures. We construct a graded connected commutative Hopf algebra $\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ whose coproduct is defined by ideal decompositions. Its character group is naturally isomorphic to $\mathrm{SL}(\mathcal{X}, K)^{\mathrm{op}}$, linking the Hopf-algebraic and unit-group viewpoints. We define a connected quotient $\mathcal{H}^c(\mathcal{X}, K)$ and show that for rooted forests it recovers the Connes–Kreimer coproduct. Finally, we prove functoriality with respect to order embeddings and determine the primitive and cocommutative cases.

2020 *Mathematics Subject Classification.* 16S99, 16T05, 16T30, 06A11, 11A25, 16U60, 20F18, 20F16, 16S37, 16S15, 16E05, 16E40, 13F55, 81T15.

Key words and phrases. poset, algebra of filters, incidence algebra, unitary convolution, arithmetical functions, group of units, nilpotent group, polycyclic group, Gröbner basis, Koszul algebra, quadratic dual, Stanley–Reisner ring, biresolution, Poincaré series, Hochschild homology, Hopf algebra, Connes–Kreimer Hopf algebra, Butcher group.

1. INTRODUCTION

The incidence algebra of a locally finite partially ordered set, introduced by Rota [13], is a fundamental object in algebraic combinatorics. It provides a unified framework for Möbius inversion, generating functions, and many counting arguments. In a different direction, the Hopf algebra of rooted trees introduced by Connes and Kreimer [5] in the context of renormalization in quantum field theory has deep connections to the earlier work of Butcher [3] on numerical integration. Both of these algebraic structures can be viewed through the lens of partially ordered sets.

In this paper, we introduce and develop the *algebra of filters* $\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ on a finite poset (\mathcal{X}, \preceq) . The underlying K -module is the free module with basis indexed by the subsets of \mathcal{X} , and the multiplication is defined by summing over ideal-filter decompositions. Our contributions are organized in four parts.

Part I: Structure and embedding (Sections 2–5). We show that Butcher’s algebra on finite labeled forests is the opposite algebra of $\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ for a natural poset of finite tuples (Proposition 3.10), thereby extending the construction from forests to arbitrary posets. Our first main result (Theorem 4.3) establishes an injective K -algebra homomorphism

$$\varphi: \mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, K) \hookrightarrow \mathbf{IA}(2^{\mathcal{X}}, \subseteq).$$

As an application, for an m -element antichain \mathcal{X} , the algebra $\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, \mathbb{C})$ is isomorphic to the algebra of arithmetical functions on the unitary divisors of $n = p_1 \cdots p_m$ under unitary convolution (Theorem 5.5).

Part II: Group of units (Sections 6–11). We undertake a detailed study of $\mathrm{GL}(\mathcal{X}, K) = \mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, K)^\times$. Our main results are:

- (1) $\mathrm{GL}(\mathcal{X}, K) \cong \mathrm{Un}(K) \times \mathrm{SL}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ (Proposition 6.3).
- (2) Every element of $\mathrm{SL}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ has a unique factorization into elementary invertible functions e_σ^k (Theorem 7.2).
- (3) $\mathrm{SL}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ is nilpotent of class at most $|\mathcal{X}|$ (Theorem 8.4).
- (4) $\mathrm{SL}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ is polycyclic if and only if $(K, +)$ is finitely generated (Theorem 9.1).
- (5) Explicit presentations for $K = \mathbb{Z}, \mathbb{Z}_m, \mathbb{Z}_{p^m}$ (Theorems 10.3 and 10.4).

Part III: Homological invariants (Sections 12–18). We establish:

- (1) The set $\mathfrak{b}(\mathcal{X})$ is a quadratic Gröbner basis for $\mathbf{AFF}(\mathcal{X})$, so $\mathbf{AF}_\bullet(\mathcal{X}, \mathbb{F})$ is Koszul (Theorem 12.2, Corollary 12.3).
- (2) The class $\mathbf{SuAlg}_{\mathbb{F}}$ of SU algebras is closed under quadratic duality (Corollary 14.3).
- (3) $\mathbf{AF}_\bullet(\mathcal{X})$ is a strictly stronger poset invariant than the Stanley–Reisner ring (Theorem 15.7).
- (4) A minimal free biresolution for $\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X})$ and the Poincaré series $(1 - t)^{-m}$ (Theorem 16.1, Proposition 17.1).

- (5) The Hochschild (co)homology and the Ext algebra (Theorem 18.3, Corollary 18.1).

Part IV: Hopf algebra structures (Sections 19–21). We construct a graded connected commutative Hopf algebra $\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ by placing the ideal-filter decomposition data in the coproduct rather than the product. The main new results are:

- (1) $\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ is a graded connected commutative Hopf algebra with recursively computable antipode (Theorem 19.4, Proposition 19.5).
- (2) The character group of $\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ is naturally isomorphic to $\text{SL}(\mathcal{X}, K)^{\text{op}}$ (Theorem 20.1).
- (3) A connected quotient $\mathcal{H}^c(\mathcal{X}, K)$ recovers the Connes–Kreimer coproduct for rooted forests (Proposition 20.5, Theorem 20.6).
- (4) The assignment $\mathcal{X} \mapsto \mathcal{H}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ is functorial for order embeddings. It is cocommutative exactly for antichains (Theorem 20.8 and Proposition 21.2).

2. PRELIMINARIES

Throughout, K denotes a commutative ring with identity, and (\mathcal{X}, \preceq) denotes a finite partially ordered set (poset). We write $x \prec y$ to mean $x \preceq y$ and $x \neq y$.

2.1. Ideals and filters.

Definition 2.1. Let (\mathcal{X}, \preceq) be a finite poset and $\sigma \subseteq \mathcal{X}$.

- (i) A subset $I \subseteq \sigma$ is an *ideal* (or *downward-closed subset*) of (σ, \preceq) if for all $x \in I$ and $y \in \sigma$, $y \preceq x$ implies $y \in I$.
- (ii) A subset $F \subseteq \sigma$ is a *filter* (or *upward-closed subset*) of (σ, \preceq) if for all $x \in F$ and $y \in \sigma$, $x \preceq y$ implies $y \in F$.

We denote by $\mathcal{I}(\sigma)$ the set of all ideals of (σ, \preceq) and by $\mathcal{F}(\sigma)$ the set of all filters.

Lemma 2.2. *If I is an ideal of (σ, \preceq) , then $F = \sigma \setminus I$ is a filter. Conversely, if F is a filter, then $I = \sigma \setminus F$ is an ideal.*

Proof. Suppose I is an ideal of σ and let $F = \sigma \setminus I$. Take $x \in F$ and $y \in \sigma$ with $x \preceq y$. If $y \in I$, then the ideal property gives $x \in I$, contradicting $x \in F$. Hence $y \in F$ and F is a filter. The converse is analogous. \square

Definition 2.3. An *ideal-filter decomposition* of $\sigma \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ is a pair (I, F) where $I \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma)$, $F \in \mathcal{F}(\sigma)$, and $I \cup F = \sigma$ with $I \cap F = \emptyset$, i.e. $\sigma = I \sqcup F$. By Lemma 2.2, specifying I uniquely determines $F = \sigma \setminus I$, so the ideal-filter decompositions of σ are in bijection with $\mathcal{I}(\sigma)$.

We denote the set of ideal-filter decompositions of σ by $\text{IFD}(\sigma)$.

Example 2.4. Let $\mathcal{X} = \{a, b, c\}$ with $a \prec b \prec c$, and $\sigma = \{a, b, c\}$. The ideals of σ are \emptyset , $\{a\}$, $\{a, b\}$, and $\{a, b, c\}$. The corresponding ideal-filter decompositions are:

$$(\emptyset, \{a, b, c\}), \quad (\{a\}, \{b, c\}), \quad (\{a, b\}, \{c\}), \quad (\{a, b, c\}, \emptyset).$$

Example 2.5. Let $\mathcal{X} = \{a, b, c\}$ be an antichain (no relations). Then every subset of σ is both an ideal and a filter, so $|\text{IFD}(\sigma)| = 2^{|\sigma|}$.

2.2. The Rota incidence algebra.

Definition 2.6. Let (P, \leq) be a locally finite poset. The *incidence algebra* $\mathbf{IA}(P, \leq)$ over K is the K -module of all functions $h: \{(x, y) \in P \times P : x \leq y\} \rightarrow K$ with the convolution product

$$(h_1 \cdot h_2)(x, y) = \sum_{x \leq z \leq y} h_1(x, z) h_2(z, y).$$

The identity element is the Kronecker delta $\delta(x, y) = 1$ if $x = y$, 0 otherwise.

When $P = 2^{\mathcal{X}}$ is the power set of a finite set \mathcal{X} ordered by inclusion \subseteq , we obtain $\mathbf{IA}(2^{\mathcal{X}}, \subseteq)$ with product

$$(h_1 \cdot h_2)(A, B) = \sum_{A \subseteq C \subseteq B} h_1(A, C) h_2(C, B).$$

2.3. The augmentation ideal and its filtration.

Lemma 2.7. Let $\varepsilon: \mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, K) \rightarrow K$ be the augmentation $\varepsilon(f) = f(\emptyset)$, and $J = \ker \varepsilon$. Then $J^n = \bigoplus_{|\sigma| \geq n} K e_\sigma$. In particular, $J^{m+1} = 0$ where $m = |\mathcal{X}|$, so J is nilpotent.

Proof. From the product formula, $e_\alpha * e_\beta \neq 0$ implies $|\alpha \cup \beta| = |\alpha| + |\beta|$ (since $\alpha \cap \beta = \emptyset$). Hence a product of n elements from J has support of size $\geq n$. Since $|\sigma| \leq m$ for all $\sigma \subseteq \mathcal{X}$, $J^{m+1} = 0$. \square

3. THE ALGEBRA OF FILTERS

3.1. Definition and basic properties.

Definition 3.1. The *algebra of filters* $\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ is the free K -module with basis $\{e_\sigma : \sigma \in 2^{\mathcal{X}}\}$, equipped with the product

$$(1) \quad (f * g)(\sigma) = \sum_{I \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma)} f(I) g(\sigma \setminus I)$$

for $f, g \in \mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ and $\sigma \subseteq \mathcal{X}$. Equivalently, the product sums over all ideal-filter decompositions (I, F) of σ the value $f(I) g(F)$.

On basis elements the product takes the form:

$$(2) \quad e_\alpha * e_\beta = \begin{cases} e_{\alpha \cup \beta} & \text{if } \alpha \cap \beta = \emptyset \text{ and } \alpha \text{ is an ideal of } (\alpha \cup \beta, \preceq), \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Remark 3.2. The condition that α is an ideal of $\alpha \cup \beta$ is equivalent to: for all $x \in \alpha$, $y \in \beta$, $y \not\prec x$.

Theorem 3.3. *The product (1) is associative and e_\emptyset is the identity element. Hence $\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ is a unital associative K -algebra.*

Proof. For $f, g, h \in \mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ and $\sigma \subseteq \mathcal{X}$:

$$((f * g) * h)(\sigma) = \sum_{\substack{J \subseteq I \subseteq \sigma \\ J \in \mathcal{I}(I), I \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma)}} f(J) g(I \setminus J) h(\sigma \setminus I),$$

and similarly

$$(f * (g * h))(\sigma) = \sum_{\substack{J \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma) \\ L \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma \setminus J)}} f(J) g(L) h(\sigma \setminus J \setminus L).$$

The bijection $(J, I) \mapsto (J, L = I \setminus J)$ between the two indexing sets establishes equality. For the identity, $(e_\emptyset * f)(\sigma) = f(\sigma)$ since $\emptyset \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma)$ for all σ and $e_\emptyset(I) = 1$ only for $I = \emptyset$. \square

Example 3.4. For $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$: $e_{\{x\}} * e_{\{y\}} = e_{\{x,y\}}$ if $x \neq y$ and $y \not\prec x$, and 0 otherwise. In particular, $e_{\{x\}}^2 = 0$. If $x \prec y$, then $e_{\{x\}} * e_{\{y\}} = e_{\{x,y\}}$ but $e_{\{y\}} * e_{\{x\}} = 0$.

3.2. The augmentation.

Definition 3.5. The *augmentation* $\varepsilon: \mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, K) \rightarrow K$ is the algebra homomorphism $\varepsilon(f) = f(\emptyset)$.

Lemma 3.6. ε is a K -algebra homomorphism with $\varepsilon(e_\emptyset) = 1$ and $\varepsilon(e_\sigma) = 0$ for $\sigma \neq \emptyset$.

Proof. $\varepsilon(f * g) = (f * g)(\emptyset) = f(\emptyset) g(\emptyset) = \varepsilon(f) \varepsilon(g)$. \square

3.3. Filtration by support.

Definition 3.7. For $n \geq 0$, let $\mathbf{AF}_n(\mathcal{X}, K) = \bigoplus_{|\sigma|=n} K e_\sigma$.

From (2), $e_\alpha * e_\beta \neq 0$ implies $|\alpha \cup \beta| = |\alpha| + |\beta|$, so $\mathbf{AF}_\bullet(\mathcal{X}, K)$ is a *graded algebra* with $\mathbf{AF}_0 \cong K$.

Proposition 3.8. $\mathbf{AF}_\bullet(\mathcal{X}, K)$ is a connected graded K -algebra with $\mathbf{AF}_n(\mathcal{X}, K)$ a free K -module of rank $\binom{m}{n}$, where $m = |\mathcal{X}|$.

Proof. By definition,

$$\mathbf{AF}_n(\mathcal{X}, K) = \bigoplus_{|\sigma|=n} K e_\sigma,$$

so it is free on the $\binom{m}{n}$ subsets of \mathcal{X} of cardinality n . \square

3.4. Factorization of basis elements.

Lemma 3.9. *Let $\sigma \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{X})$ be nonempty, and let $x_1 <_0 x_2 <_0 \cdots <_0 x_n$ be any linear extension of (σ, \preceq) . Then*

$$e_\sigma = e_{\{x_1\}} * e_{\{x_2\}} * \cdots * e_{\{x_n\}}.$$

In particular, $\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ is generated by $\{e_{\{x\}} : x \in \mathcal{X}\}$.

Proof. Induction on $n = |\sigma|$. Since $<_0$ is a linear extension of \preceq , the set $\sigma_i = \{x_1, \dots, x_i\}$ is an ideal of (σ_{i+1}, \preceq) , so $e_{\sigma_i} * e_{\{x_{i+1}\}} = e_{\sigma_{i+1}}$. The claim follows. \square

3.5. Connection to Butcher's algebra on forests. The algebra of filters generalizes a construction of Butcher [3]. Let \mathbb{N}^* denote the set of all finite tuples of natural numbers. The set \mathbf{FF} of *finite labeled forests* consists of all finite subsets of \mathbb{N}^* . For $\sigma', \sigma \in \mathbf{FF}$, write $\sigma' \leq_i \sigma$ if $\sigma' \subseteq \sigma$ and for every $x \in \sigma'$, $x^- \in \sigma$ implies $x^- \in \sigma'$. Butcher defined the product

$$(3) \quad (f \cdot_B g)(\sigma) = \sum_{\sigma' \leq_i \sigma} f(\sigma \setminus \sigma') g(\sigma')$$

on $\mathbb{R}^{\mathbf{FF}}$. Comparing with (1), Butcher evaluates f on the filter and g on the ideal, so his product is opposite to ours.

Proposition 3.10. *Let \preceq be the transitive reflexive closure of $\{(x^-, x)\}_{x \in \mathbb{N}^*}$. Then $(\mathbb{R}^{\mathbf{FF}}, \cdot_B) \cong \mathbf{AF}(\mathbb{N}^*, \preceq, \mathbb{R})^{\text{op}}$.*

Proof. The ideals of (σ, \preceq) are exactly the σ' with $\sigma' \leq_i \sigma$. Substituting $I = \sigma'$, $(f \cdot_B g)(\sigma) = \sum_{I \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma)} f(\sigma \setminus I) g(I) = (g * f)(\sigma)$, so the identity map is an isomorphism to the opposite algebra. \square

The algebra of filters thus provides a unified poset-theoretic framework encompassing both Butcher's algebra and the structures underlying the Connes–Kreimer Hopf algebra [5].

4. EMBEDDING INTO THE INCIDENCE ALGEBRA

4.1. Construction of the homomorphism.

Definition 4.1. Define $\varphi: \mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, K) \rightarrow \mathbf{IA}(2^{\mathcal{X}}, \subseteq)$ by

$$(4) \quad \varphi(e_\sigma)(\sigma', \tau) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \tau \setminus \sigma' = \sigma \text{ and } \sigma' \in \mathcal{I}(\tau), \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

extended by linearity.

Lemma 4.2. *The map φ is a K -algebra homomorphism.*

Proof. For $\sigma' \subseteq \tau$,

$$(\varphi(f) \cdot \varphi(g))(\sigma', \tau) = \sum_{\sigma' \subseteq \rho \subseteq \tau} \varphi(f)(\sigma', \rho) \varphi(g)(\rho, \tau).$$

A term is nonzero only if $\sigma' \in \mathcal{I}(\rho)$ and $\rho \in \mathcal{I}(\tau)$, in which case $\sigma' \in \mathcal{I}(\tau)$ by transitivity. Setting $I = \rho \setminus \sigma'$, as ρ ranges over valid intermediate sets, I ranges over all ideals of $\tau \setminus \sigma'$. Hence $(\varphi(f) \cdot \varphi(g))(\sigma', \tau) = \sum_{I \in \mathcal{I}(\tau \setminus \sigma')} f(I) g(\tau \setminus \sigma' \setminus I) = \varphi(f * g)(\sigma', \tau)$. \square

Theorem 4.3 (Embedding theorem). *The homomorphism φ is injective.*

Proof. Suppose $\varphi(f) = 0$. For each $\sigma \subseteq \mathcal{X}$, $\varphi(f)(\emptyset, \sigma) = f(\sigma)$ since $\emptyset \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma)$. Hence $f(\sigma) = 0$ for all σ . \square

Remark 4.4. The image of φ consists of those $h \in \mathbf{IA}(2^{\mathcal{X}}, \subseteq)$ such that $h(\sigma', \tau) = 0$ unless $\sigma' \in \mathcal{I}(\tau)$, and $h(\sigma', \tau)$ depends only on $\tau \setminus \sigma'$.

Remark 4.5 (Representation of the Butcher group). Since φ is injective, it restricts to a faithful representation

$$\varphi|_{\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, K)^\times} : \mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, K)^\times \hookrightarrow \mathbf{IA}(2^{\mathcal{X}}, \subseteq)^\times.$$

For the infinite tree poset $\mathcal{X} = \mathbb{N}^*$ one should interpret this through finite truncations: each finite induced subposet admits such a faithful representation, and these representations are compatible with the truncation maps used in Butcher theory.

Proposition 4.6. *The image of φ is the subalgebra of $\mathbf{IA}(2^{\mathcal{X}}, \subseteq)$ consisting of all h such that $h(\sigma', \tau) = 0$ whenever $\sigma' \notin \mathcal{I}(\tau)$, and $h(\sigma', \tau)$ depends only on $\tau \setminus \sigma'$.*

Proof. If $h = \varphi(f)$, then (4) shows immediately that $h(\sigma', \tau) = 0$ unless $\sigma' \in \mathcal{I}(\tau)$, and in the allowed case $h(\sigma', \tau) = f(\tau \setminus \sigma')$, so it depends only on the set difference.

Conversely, let h satisfy the stated conditions and define $f(\sigma) = h(\emptyset, \sigma)$. Since $\emptyset \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma)$ for every $\sigma \subseteq \mathcal{X}$, the dependence-on-difference condition gives

$$h(\sigma', \tau) = h(\emptyset, \tau \setminus \sigma') = f(\tau \setminus \sigma')$$

whenever $\sigma' \in \mathcal{I}(\tau)$, and both sides vanish otherwise. Hence $h = \varphi(f)$. \square

Proof. Given such an h , define $f(\sigma) = h(\emptyset, \sigma)$. Then $\varphi(f) = h$. \square

5. ARITHMETICAL FUNCTIONS AND UNITARY CONVOLUTION

5.1. Unitary divisors and unitary convolution.

Definition 5.1. An integer d is a *unitary divisor* of n , written $d||n$, if $d | n$ and $\gcd(d, n/d) = 1$. We denote by $\text{udiv}(n)$ the set of unitary divisors of n .

Definition 5.2. The *unitary convolution* of arithmetical functions $f, g: \mathbb{N}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ [4, 18] is

$$(f \star g)(n) = \sum_{d||n} f(d) g(n/d).$$

5.2. The poset of unitary divisors.

Proposition 5.3. *Let $n = p_1^{a_1} \cdots p_m^{a_m}$. Define $\psi: \text{udiv}(n) \rightarrow 2^{\{p_1, \dots, p_m\}}$ by $\psi(d) = \{p_i : p_i^{a_i} \mid d\}$. Then ψ is a poset isomorphism $(\text{udiv}(n), \parallel) \cong (2^{\{p_1, \dots, p_m\}}, \subseteq)$.*

Proof. Each unitary divisor $d \parallel n$ has the form $d = \prod_{i \in S} p_i^{a_i}$ for a unique $S \subseteq \{1, \dots, m\}$, and $d \parallel e$ iff the prime support of d is contained in that of e . \square

5.3. The antichain case. Let \mathbb{P} denote a countable set with no order relations (an antichain). When \mathcal{X} is an m -element antichain, every subset of \mathcal{X} is both an ideal and a filter, so the product (1) becomes

$$(f * g)(\sigma) = \sum_{\alpha \subseteq \sigma} f(\alpha) g(\sigma \setminus \alpha),$$

the convolution over the Boolean lattice $(2^{\mathcal{X}}, \subseteq)$.

Lemma 5.4. *Let \mathcal{X} be a finite antichain with $|\mathcal{X}| = m$, and let $n = p_1 \cdots p_m$ be squarefree. Then the map $f \mapsto f \circ \psi$ defines a \mathbb{C} -algebra isomorphism $\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, \mathbb{C}) \cong (\mathbb{C}^{\text{udiv}(n)}, \star)$.*

Theorem 5.5. *Let \mathcal{X} be a finite antichain with $|\mathcal{X}| = m$, and let $n = p_1 \cdots p_m$ be the product of the first m primes. Then there is an isomorphism of \mathbb{C} -algebras*

$$\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, \mathbb{C}) \cong (\mathbb{C}^{\text{udiv}(n)}, \star).$$

Proof. By Proposition 5.3, $(\text{udiv}(n), \parallel) \cong (2^{\mathcal{X}}, \subseteq)$ via ψ . Send $f \in \mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, \mathbb{C})$ to $\tilde{f}(d) = f(\psi(d))$. Then

$$\widetilde{f * g}(d) = \sum_{\alpha \subseteq \psi(d)} f(\alpha) g(\psi(d) \setminus \alpha) = \sum_{e \parallel d} \tilde{f}(e) \tilde{g}(d/e) = (\tilde{f} \star \tilde{g})(d). \quad \square$$

Example 5.6. Take $n = 30 = 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 5$. Then $\mathcal{X} = \{2, 3, 5\}$ is a 3-element antichain, and

$$\text{udiv}(30) = \{1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 10, 15, 30\}.$$

If $f = \sum r_i e_i$ and $g = \sum s_i e_i$ (where e_i stands for $e_{\psi(i)}$), then

$$f \star g(30) = r_1 s_{30} + r_2 s_{15} + r_3 s_{10} + r_5 s_6 + r_6 s_5 + r_{10} s_3 + r_{15} s_2 + r_{30} s_1.$$

6. THE GROUP OF UNITS

6.1. Structure of $\text{GL}(\mathcal{X}, K)$.

Definition 6.1. (i) $\text{GL}(\mathcal{X}, K) = \mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, K)^\times$, the group of invertible elements.

(ii) $\text{SL}(\mathcal{X}, K) = \{f \in \text{GL}(\mathcal{X}, K) : \varepsilon(f) = 1\}$.

Proposition 6.2. *An element $f \in \mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ is invertible if and only if $f(\emptyset) \in \text{Un}(K)$.*

Proof. If f is invertible then $f(\emptyset) \in \text{Un}(K)$. Conversely, writing $f = u e_\emptyset + h$ with $u = f(\emptyset) \in \text{Un}(K)$ and $h \in \ker \varepsilon$, Lemma 2.7 gives $(u^{-1}h)^{m+1} = 0$, so $f^{-1} = u^{-1} \sum_{j=0}^m (-u^{-1}h)^j$. \square

Proposition 6.3. $\text{GL}(\mathcal{X}, K) \cong \text{Un}(K) \times \text{SL}(\mathcal{X}, K)$.

Proof. The map $f \mapsto (\varepsilon(f), \varepsilon(f)^{-1}f)$ is a group isomorphism with inverse $(u, g) \mapsto ug$. \square

6.2. Elementary invertible functions.

Definition 6.4. For $\sigma \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{X}) \setminus \{\emptyset\}$ and $k \in K$, the *elementary invertible function* $e_\sigma^k \in \text{SL}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ is

$$e_\sigma^k = e_\emptyset + k e_\sigma.$$

Lemma 6.5. Let $\sigma, \tau \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{X}) \setminus \{\emptyset\}$ and $k, l \in K$.

- (i) $(e_\sigma^k)^{-1} = e_\sigma^{-k}$.
- (ii) $e_\sigma^k * e_\sigma^l = e_\sigma^{k+l}$.
- (iii) If $\sigma \cap \tau = \emptyset$ and $\sigma \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma \cup \tau)$, then $e_\sigma^k * e_\tau^l = e_\tau^l * e_\sigma^k * e_{\sigma \cup \tau}^{kl}$.
- (iv) If $\sigma \cap \tau \neq \emptyset$, then $e_\sigma^k * e_\tau^l = e_\tau^l * e_\sigma^k$.
- (v) If $\sigma \cap \tau = \emptyset$ and neither is an ideal of $\sigma \cup \tau$, then $e_\sigma^k * e_\tau^l = e_\tau^l * e_\sigma^k$.

Proof. (i) Direct computation. (ii) $(e_\sigma^k * e_\sigma^l)(\sigma) = l + k$. (iii) One computes both sides at each $\rho \in \{\emptyset, \sigma, \tau, \sigma \cup \tau\}$; at $\rho = \sigma \cup \tau$, $(e_\sigma^k * e_\tau^l)(\sigma \cup \tau) = kl$ (from $I = \sigma$), while $(e_\tau^l * e_\sigma^k)(\sigma \cup \tau) = 0$, and adding $e_{\sigma \cup \tau}^{kl}$ restores equality. (iv)–(v) No $\sigma \sqcup \tau = \sigma \cup \tau$ decomposition contributes, so both sides agree directly. \square

7. UNIQUE FACTORIZATION

Definition 7.1. Fix a linear extension $<_0$ of (\mathcal{X}, \preceq) . Order the nonempty subsets of \mathcal{X} by the *shortlex order*: $\sigma < \tau$ if $|\sigma| < |\tau|$, or $|\sigma| = |\tau|$ and σ precedes τ lexicographically with respect to $<_0$.

Let $\sigma_1 < \sigma_2 < \dots < \sigma_{2^m-1}$ be the nonempty subsets of \mathcal{X} in shortlex order.

Theorem 7.2 (Unique factorization). *Every element $f \in \text{SL}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ has a unique expression*

$$f = e_{\sigma_1}^{k_1} * e_{\sigma_2}^{k_2} * \dots * e_{\sigma_{2^m-1}}^{k_{2^m-1}}, \quad k_i \in K.$$

Proof. Existence. Set $k_1 = f(\sigma_1)$ and $f_1 = e_{\sigma_1}^{-k_1} * f$. Inductively, set $k_j = f_{j-1}(\sigma_j)$ and $f_j = e_{\sigma_j}^{-k_j} * f_{j-1}$. Multiplying by $e_{\sigma_j}^{-k_j}$ does not disturb previously zeroed components (no contributions at smaller subsets). After $2^m - 1$ steps, $f_{2^m-1} = e_\emptyset$.

Uniqueness. Evaluate at σ_1 to get $k_1 = l_1$, then multiply on the left by $e_{\sigma_1}^{-k_1}$ and proceed inductively. \square

Corollary 7.3. *The map $(k_1, \dots, k_{2^m-1}) \mapsto e_{\sigma_1}^{k_1} * \dots * e_{\sigma_{2^m-1}}^{k_{2^m-1}}$ is a bijection $K^{2^m-1} \rightarrow \text{SL}(\mathcal{X}, K)$.*

8. NILPOTENCY

Definition 8.1. For $n \geq 1$, let $\mathrm{SL}_n(\mathcal{X}, K) = \mathrm{SL}(\mathcal{X}, K) \cap (e_\emptyset + (\ker \varepsilon)^n)$; equivalently, $f \in \mathrm{SL}_n$ iff $f(\emptyset) = 1$ and $f(\sigma) = 0$ for $0 < |\sigma| < n$.

Lemma 8.2. Each $\mathrm{SL}_n(\mathcal{X}, K)$ is a normal subgroup of $\mathrm{SL}(\mathcal{X}, K)$, with $\mathrm{SL}_1 = \mathrm{SL}$ and $\mathrm{SL}_{m+1} = \{e_\emptyset\}$.

Lemma 8.3. The quotient $\mathrm{SL}_n(\mathcal{X}, K) / \mathrm{SL}_{n+1}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ is abelian.

Proof. For $f = e_\emptyset + \hat{f}$, $g = e_\emptyset + \hat{g}$ with $\hat{f}, \hat{g} \in (\ker \varepsilon)^n$: $f * g = e_\emptyset + \hat{f} + \hat{g} + \hat{f} * \hat{g}$, and $\hat{f} * \hat{g} \in (\ker \varepsilon)^{2n} \subseteq (\ker \varepsilon)^{n+1}$. Hence $f * g \equiv g * f \pmod{\mathrm{SL}_{n+1}}$. \square

Theorem 8.4. Let $|\mathcal{X}| = m \geq 1$. Then $\mathrm{SL}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ is nilpotent of class at most m , with $\gamma_n(\mathrm{SL}(\mathcal{X}, K)) \leq \mathrm{SL}_n(\mathcal{X}, K)$ for all $n \geq 1$.

Proof. Write $J = \mathrm{Ker} \varepsilon$. If $f = e_\emptyset + \hat{f} \in \mathrm{SL}_n = e_\emptyset + J^n$ and $g = e_\emptyset + \hat{g} \in \mathrm{SL}_p = e_\emptyset + J^p$, then their inverses also have the form $f^{-1} = e_\emptyset + u$ with $u \in J^n$ and $g^{-1} = e_\emptyset + v$ with $v \in J^p$, because J is nilpotent. Therefore every nonconstant term in the expansion of $[f, g] = f^{-1}g^{-1}fg$ contains at least one factor from J^n and at least one factor from J^p , so $[f, g] - e_\emptyset \in J^{n+p}$. Equivalently, $[\mathrm{SL}_n, \mathrm{SL}_p] \leq \mathrm{SL}_{n+p}$.

Now $\gamma_1(\mathrm{SL}) = \mathrm{SL} = \mathrm{SL}_1$, and if $\gamma_n(\mathrm{SL}) \leq \mathrm{SL}_n$ then

$$\gamma_{n+1}(\mathrm{SL}) = [\gamma_n(\mathrm{SL}), \mathrm{SL}] \leq [\mathrm{SL}_n, \mathrm{SL}_1] \leq \mathrm{SL}_{n+1}.$$

Hence $\gamma_n(\mathrm{SL}) \leq \mathrm{SL}_n$ for all n . Since $\mathrm{SL}_{m+1} = \{e_\emptyset\}$, we get $\gamma_{m+1}(\mathrm{SL}) = \{e_\emptyset\}$, so $\mathrm{SL}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ is nilpotent of class at most m . \square

Remark 8.5. More precisely, $[\mathrm{SL}_n, \mathrm{SL}_p] \leq \mathrm{SL}_{n+p}$, so $\gamma_n(\mathrm{SL}) \leq \mathrm{SL}_n$ for all n .

Corollary 8.6. $\mathrm{SL}_n(\mathcal{X}, K) / \mathrm{SL}_{n+1}(\mathcal{X}, K) \cong (K, +)^{\binom{m}{n}}$ for $1 \leq n \leq m$.

Proof. The map $f \mapsto (f(\sigma))_{|\sigma|=n}$ is a group isomorphism from $\mathrm{SL}_n / \mathrm{SL}_{n+1}$ to $\bigoplus_{|\sigma|=n} K$. \square

9. POLYCYCLICITY AND STRUCTURE

A group G is *polycyclic* if it admits a subnormal series with cyclic quotients. A group is *poly-* $(K, +)$ if it has a subnormal series with quotients isomorphic to $(K, +)$.

Theorem 9.1. Let $|\mathcal{X}| = m \geq 1$.

- (i) $\mathrm{SL}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ is *poly-* $(K, +)$ of length $2^m - 1$.
- (ii) $\mathrm{SL}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ is *polycyclic* if and only if $(K, +)$ is *finitely generated*.
- (iii) If $K = \mathbb{Z}$, then $\mathrm{SL}(\mathcal{X}, \mathbb{Z})$ is *torsion-free polycyclic*.
- (iv) If $K = \mathbb{Z}_n$ with n a prime power, then $\mathrm{SL}(\mathcal{X}, \mathbb{Z}_n)$ is a *finite p-group*.

Proof. (i) By Corollary 8.6, each factor $\mathrm{SL}_n / \mathrm{SL}_{n+1}$ is isomorphic to a direct sum of $\binom{m}{n}$ copies of $(K, +)$. Refining each such direct sum by its coordinate flag yields a subnormal series whose successive quotients are all isomorphic to $(K, +)$. The total length is $\sum_{n=1}^m \binom{m}{n} = 2^m - 1$. (ii) If $\mathrm{SL}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ is

polycyclic, then every quotient is polycyclic, so in particular $\mathrm{SL}_1 / \mathrm{SL}_2 \cong (K, +)^m$ is polycyclic. Hence $(K, +)$ is a quotient of a polycyclic group and is therefore finitely generated. Conversely, if $(K, +)$ is finitely generated, then every finite direct sum $(K, +)^r$ is polycyclic. Applying this to the factors $\mathrm{SL}_n / \mathrm{SL}_{n+1}$ and refining the filtration above gives a polycyclic series for $\mathrm{SL}(\mathcal{X}, K)$. (iii) $(\mathbb{Z}, +)$ is torsion-free cyclic. (iv) Here $(\mathbb{Z}_n, +)$ is a finite p -group, so each successive quotient in the refined series is a finite cyclic p -group. Hence $\mathrm{SL}(\mathcal{X}, \mathbb{Z}_n)$ is a finite p -group. \square

For background on polycyclic groups and nilpotent group theory see e.g. [9, 15].

10. EXPLICIT PRESENTATIONS

10.1. Commutator relations.

Definition 10.1. Two nonempty subsets $\sigma, \tau \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ form a *compatible pair* if $\sigma \cap \tau = \emptyset$ and $\sigma \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma \cup \tau)$. We write $\sigma \ll \tau$.

Proposition 10.2. For $\sigma, \tau \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{X}) \setminus \{\emptyset\}$ and $k, l \in K$:

$$[e_\sigma^k, e_\tau^l] = \begin{cases} e_{\sigma \cup \tau}^{kl} & \text{if } \sigma \ll \tau, \\ e_{\sigma \cup \tau}^{-kl} & \text{if } \tau \ll \sigma, \\ e_\emptyset & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

where $[a, b] = a^{-1}b^{-1}ab$.

Proof. If $\sigma \ll \tau$, then Lemma 6.5(iii) gives $e_\sigma^k * e_\tau^l = e_\tau^l * e_\sigma^k * e_{\sigma \cup \tau}^{kl}$, so $[e_\sigma^k, e_\tau^l] = e_{\sigma \cup \tau}^{kl}$. The other cases are analogous. \square

10.2. Presentation over \mathbb{Z} .

Theorem 10.3. Let $|\mathcal{X}| = m$ and list the nonempty subsets as $\sigma_1 < \sigma_2 < \dots < \sigma_{2^m-1}$ in shortlex order. Then $\mathrm{SL}(\mathcal{X}, \mathbb{Z})$ has the presentation with:

Generators: $\{a_i : 1 \leq i \leq 2^m - 1\}$, where a_i corresponds to $e_{\sigma_i}^1$.

Relations:

- (R1) $[a_i, a_j] = a_k^\epsilon$ whenever $\sigma_i \ll \sigma_j$ or $\sigma_j \ll \sigma_i$, where $\sigma_k = \sigma_i \cup \sigma_j$ and $\epsilon = +1$ if $\sigma_i \ll \sigma_j$, -1 if $\sigma_j \ll \sigma_i$.
- (R2) $[a_i, a_j] = 1$ otherwise.

Proof. The relations follow from Proposition 10.2. Sufficiency uses the collection process for polycyclic presentations (see e.g. [15]). \square

10.3. Presentation over \mathbb{Z}_n .

Theorem 10.4. $\mathrm{SL}(\mathcal{X}, \mathbb{Z}_n)$ has the same generators and relations as in Theorem 10.3, together with:

- (R3) $a_i^n = 1$ for all $1 \leq i \leq 2^m - 1$.

In particular, $|\mathrm{SL}(\mathcal{X}, \mathbb{Z}_n)| = n^{2^m-1}$.

11. EXAMPLES

Example 11.1 (Chain of length 2). Let $\mathcal{X} = \{a, b\}$ with $a \prec b$. Since $\{a\} \ll \{b\}$, the single nontrivial commutator is $[e_{\{a\}}^k, e_{\{b\}}^l] = e_{\{a,b\}}^{kl}$. Over \mathbb{Z} : $\mathrm{SL}(\mathcal{X}, \mathbb{Z}) \cong \langle a_1, a_2, a_3 \mid [a_1, a_2] = a_3, [a_1, a_3] = 1, [a_2, a_3] = 1 \rangle$, the Heisenberg group $H_3(\mathbb{Z})$.

Example 11.2 (Antichain of size 2). Let $\mathcal{X} = \{a, b\}$ with no relations. Both $\{a\} \ll \{b\}$ and $\{b\} \ll \{a\}$ hold, so $[e_{\{a\}}^k, e_{\{b\}}^l] = e_\emptyset$. Over \mathbb{Z} , $\mathrm{SL}(\mathcal{X}, \mathbb{Z}) \cong H_3(\mathbb{Z})$.

Example 11.3 (Chain of length 3). Let $\mathcal{X} = \{a, b, c\}$ with $a \prec b \prec c$. There are $2^3 - 1 = 7$ nonempty subsets. Compatible pairs include $\{a\} \ll \{b\}$, $\{a\} \ll \{c\}$, $\{b\} \ll \{c\}$, $\{a\} \ll \{b, c\}$, $\{a, b\} \ll \{c\}$. Over \mathbb{Z} , $\mathrm{SL}(\mathcal{X}, \mathbb{Z})$ is nilpotent of class 3 with 7 generators.

12. PRESENTATION AND GRÖBNER BASIS

12.1. The presentation of $\mathbf{AFF}(\mathcal{X})$. Let (\mathcal{X}, \preceq) be a finite poset with a compatible well-order $<_0$ (a total order with $x \prec y \Rightarrow x <_0 y$; every finite poset admits one).

Definition 12.1. Define the set of monic quadratic polynomials

$$(5) \quad \mathfrak{b}(\mathcal{X}) = \{yx - xy \mid x \not\preceq y, x <_0 y\} \cup \{yx \mid x \preceq y\}$$

in $K\langle \mathcal{X} \rangle$. The first family says incomparable generators commute; the second says products in reverse order (filter before ideal) vanish.

Theorem 12.2 (Presentation and Gröbner basis). *Let (\mathcal{X}, \preceq) be a finite poset with compatible well-order $<_0$.*

- (i) *The set $\mathfrak{b}(\mathcal{X})$ is a Gröbner basis for $\mathbf{AFF}(\mathcal{X})$.*
- (ii) $\mathbf{AFF}(\mathcal{X}) \cong K\langle \mathcal{X} \mid \mathfrak{b}(\mathcal{X}) \rangle$.

Proof. We apply the diamond lemma of Bergman [2]. The rewriting system $\mathbf{rws}(\mathcal{X}, \mathfrak{b}(\mathcal{X}), <_0)$ has rules: (a) $yx \rightarrow xy$ if $x \not\preceq y, x <_0 y$; (b) $yx \rightarrow 0$ if $x \preceq y$. This is Noetherian (each step reduces the length-lexicographic order or sends to zero). For confluence we check all critical pairs on words zyx by cases on the comparability of $\{x, y, z\}$: in every case both reduction paths reach the same normal form. Hence $\mathfrak{b}(\mathcal{X})$ is a Gröbner basis. The normal forms are words $x_1 \cdots x_n$ with $x_1 <_0 \cdots <_0 x_n$, in bijection with subsets of \mathcal{X} , confirming $\dim \mathbf{AFF}_n = \binom{m}{n}$. \square

12.2. Koszulity.

Corollary 12.3. *For any field \mathbb{F} , the graded algebra $\mathbf{AF}_\bullet(\mathcal{X}, \mathbb{F})$ is Koszul.*

Proof. By Theorem 12.2, $\mathbf{AF}_\bullet(\mathcal{X}, \mathbb{F})$ has a quadratic Gröbner basis. A quadratic algebra with a quadratic Gröbner basis has a minimal linear Anick resolution [1], hence is Koszul [12]. \square

13. SU ALGEBRAS

13.1. SU matrices and SU algebras.

Definition 13.1. Let X be a set with well-order $<_0$. A function $\phi: X \times X \rightarrow K$ is an *SU matrix* if:

- (i) $\phi(x, y) = \phi(y, x)$ for all x, y (symmetric);
- (ii) $\phi(x, x) \in \{0, 1\}$ for all x .

The *SU algebra* $\mathcal{A}(X, \phi, <_0, K)$ is

$$(6) \quad K\langle X ; yx - \phi(x, y)xy \ (x <_0 y), \quad x^2 \ (\phi(x, x) = 0) \rangle.$$

We write \mathbf{SuAlg}_K for the class of all SU algebras over K .

Example 13.2. Taking $\phi = \chi_{\not\leq}$ (the characteristic function of the incomparability relation), $\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{X}, \phi, <_0, K) \cong \mathbf{AFF}(\mathcal{X}, K)$.

Example 13.3. The polynomial algebra $\mathbb{F}[y_1, \dots, y_m]$ comes from $\phi \equiv 1$. The exterior algebra $\bigwedge(x_1, \dots, x_m)$ comes from $\phi(x_i, x_j) = -1$ for $i \neq j$, $\phi(x_i, x_i) = 0$.

Example 13.4. The quantum plane $\mathbb{F}\langle x, y; yx - qxy \rangle$ is the SU algebra for $\phi(x, y) = q$, $\phi(x, x) = \phi(y, y) = 1$.

Lemma 13.5 (Completeness for SU algebras). *For any SU quadruple, the set $\mathfrak{b}(X, \phi, <_0) = \{yx - \phi(x, y)xy \mid x <_0 y\} \cup \{x^2 \mid \phi(x, x) = 0\}$ is a Gröbner basis.*

Proof. Check all critical pairs on words zyx :

- (1) $x <_0 y <_0 z$: both paths give $\phi(x, z)\phi(x, y)\phi(y, z) \cdot xyz$.
- (2) yyx , $\phi(y, y) = 0$: $y^2x \rightarrow 0$; and $y(yx) \rightarrow \phi(x, y)^2xyy \rightarrow 0$.
- (3) yxx , $\phi(x, x) = 0$: both paths give 0.
- (4) xxx , $\phi(x, x) = 0$: both paths give 0.

All critical pairs resolve. □

Corollary 13.6. *Every SU algebra over a field with a finite SU quadruple is Koszul.*

14. QUADRATIC DUALITY

14.1. The quadratic dual of an SU algebra.

Definition 14.1. The *dual* of an SU matrix ϕ is

$$\phi^!(x, y) = \begin{cases} -\phi(y, x) & x \neq y, \\ 1 - \phi(y, x) & x = y. \end{cases}$$

Theorem 14.2. *Let $(X, \phi, <_0, \mathbb{F})$ be a finite SU quadruple over a field \mathbb{F} . Then $\mathcal{A}_\bullet^!(X, \phi, <_0) \cong \mathcal{A}_\bullet(X, \phi^!, <_0^{\text{opp}})$.*

Proof. The quadratic dual has $(I_2)^! = \text{Ann}(I_2) \subseteq (A_1 \otimes A_1)^*$. An element $f = \sum k_{xy}(xy)^*$ lies in $\text{Ann}(I_2)$ iff $k_{yx} = \phi(x, y)k_{xy}$ for $x <_0 y$ and $k_{xx} = 0$ when $\phi(x, x) = 0$. The resulting dual algebra has presentation $\mathbb{F}\langle X; xy + \phi(x, y)yx \ (x <_0 y), x^2 \ (\phi(x, x) \neq 0) \rangle$. Rewriting under $<_0^{\text{opp}}$ and using $\phi^!(x, y) = -\phi(x, y)$ for $x \neq y$ (by symmetry) gives the claim. \square

Corollary 14.3. $\text{SuAlg}_{\mathbb{F}}$ is closed under quadratic duality.

Proof. $\phi^!$ is again an SU matrix: symmetric, and $\phi^!(x, x) = 1 - \phi(x, x) \in \{0, 1\}$. \square

Proposition 14.4. $\mathbf{AF}_{\bullet}^!(\mathcal{X}) \cong \mathbb{F}\langle \mathcal{X}; xy + yx \ (x \not\prec y), xy \ (x \prec y) \rangle$.

Proof. For $\mathbf{AFF}(\mathcal{X})$, the associated SU matrix is

$$\phi(x, y) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \not\prec y, \\ 0 & \text{if } x \prec y \text{ or } y \prec x, \end{cases}$$

with $\phi(x, x) = 0$. By Theorem 14.2, the quadratic dual is the SU algebra for $\phi^!$ with respect to the opposite order. Thus incomparable pairs contribute the relation $xy + yx$, while comparable pairs contribute the monomial relation $xy = 0$ in the appropriate order, namely for $x \prec y$. \square

Remark 14.5. $\mathbf{AF}_{\bullet}(\mathcal{X})$ is generally not isomorphic to its quadratic dual: for $\mathcal{X} = \{x\}$, $\mathbf{AF}_{\bullet}(\{x\}) = \mathbb{F}\langle x; x^2 \rangle$ (finite-dimensional) but $\mathbf{AF}_{\bullet}^!(\{x\}) = \mathbb{F}\langle x \rangle$ (infinite-dimensional).

15. STANLEY–REISNER RINGS AND \mathbf{AF}_{\bullet} AS A POSET INVARIANT

15.1. The abelianization and Stanley–Reisner ring.

Definition 15.1. The *abelianization* of $\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X})$ is $\mathbf{AF}^{\text{ab}}(\mathcal{X}) \cong K[\mathcal{X}; (1 - \chi_{\not\prec}(x, y))xy, \forall x, y]$: the monomial xy is killed iff x and y are comparable.

Definition 15.2. The *Stanley–Reisner ring* [16] of (\mathcal{X}, \preceq) over \mathbb{F} is $\mathbf{SR}(\mathcal{X}, \mathbb{F}) = \mathbb{F}[\mathcal{X}; \chi_{\not\prec}(x, y)xy, \forall x, y]$: the monomial xy is killed iff x and y are *incomparable*.

Remark 15.3. $\mathbf{AF}^{\text{ab}}(\mathcal{X})$ encodes the *comparability graph*, while $\mathbf{SR}(\mathcal{X})$ encodes the *incomparability graph*—complementary presentations.

15.2. Antichains and graded components.

Definition 15.4. A subset $\sigma \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ is an *antichain* if distinct elements of σ are pairwise incomparable. The *width* $\mathbf{w}(\mathcal{X})$ is the maximum antichain size.

Proposition 15.5. $\mathbf{AF}_n^{\text{ab}}(\mathcal{X})$ is the free K -module on the antichains of \mathcal{X} of cardinality n ; in particular $\mathbf{AF}_n^{\text{ab}}(\mathcal{X}) = 0$ for $n > \mathbf{w}(\mathcal{X})$.

Proposition 15.6. A graded isomorphism $\mathbf{AF}_{\bullet}^{\text{ab}}(\mathcal{X}) \cong \mathbf{AF}_{\bullet}^{\text{ab}}(\mathcal{Y})$ implies $|\mathcal{X}| = |\mathcal{Y}|$ and $\mathbf{w}(\mathcal{X}) = \mathbf{w}(\mathcal{Y})$.

15.3. \mathbf{AF}_\bullet is a strictly stronger invariant.

Theorem 15.7. *There exist finite posets \mathcal{Y} and \mathcal{Z} such that:*

- (i) $\mathbf{AF}_\bullet^{\text{ab}}(\mathcal{Y}, K) \cong \mathbf{AF}_\bullet^{\text{ab}}(\mathcal{Z}, K)$ for any commutative ring K .
- (ii) $\mathbf{SR}_\bullet(\mathcal{Y}, \mathbb{F}) \cong \mathbf{SR}_\bullet(\mathcal{Z}, \mathbb{F})$ for any field \mathbb{F} .
- (iii) $\mathbf{AF}_\bullet(\mathcal{Y}, \mathbb{F}) \not\cong \mathbf{AF}_\bullet(\mathcal{Z}, \mathbb{F})$ for any field \mathbb{F} .

Proof. Let $\mathcal{Y} = \{x_1, x_2, x_3\}$ with $x_1 \prec x_2, x_1 \prec x_3$ (“V” poset), and $\mathcal{Z} = \{y_1, y_2, y_3\}$ with $y_2 \prec y_1, y_3 \prec y_1$ (“Λ” poset, dual of \mathcal{Y}).

(i)–(ii) Both posets have the same incomparability graph (edge $\{x_2, x_3\}$ respectively $\{y_2, y_3\}$), so both $\mathbf{AF}_\bullet^{\text{ab}}$ and \mathbf{SR} are isomorphic.

(iii) $\mathbf{AF}_\bullet(\mathcal{Y})$ has presentation $\mathbb{F}\langle x_1, x_2, x_3; x_2x_1, x_3x_1, x_3x_2 - x_2x_3, x_i^2 \rangle$, while in $\mathbf{AF}_\bullet(\mathcal{Z})$ the vanishing relations are y_1y_2 and y_1y_3 instead.

Consider the degree-one left and right annihilator spaces

$$L_1(A) = \{a \in A_1 : aA_1 = 0\}, \quad R_1(A) = \{a \in A_1 : A_1a = 0\}.$$

These are preserved by graded algebra isomorphisms. In $\mathbf{AF}_\bullet(\mathcal{Y})$, $R_1(\mathbf{AF}_\bullet(\mathcal{Y})) = \mathbb{F}x_1$ because $x_1^2 = x_2x_1 = x_3x_1 = 0$, while $L_1(\mathbf{AF}_\bullet(\mathcal{Y})) = 0$ since x_1x_2 and x_1x_3 are nonzero and $x_2x_3 = x_3x_2$ is nonzero. Dually, in $\mathbf{AF}_\bullet(\mathcal{Z})$ one has $L_1(\mathbf{AF}_\bullet(\mathcal{Z})) = \mathbb{F}y_1$ and $R_1(\mathbf{AF}_\bullet(\mathcal{Z})) = 0$. Therefore $\mathbf{AF}_\bullet(\mathcal{Y})$ and $\mathbf{AF}_\bullet(\mathcal{Z})$ cannot be isomorphic as graded algebras. \square

16. THE MINIMAL BIREOLUTION

16.1. Construction. Let (X, ϕ, \prec_0, K) be an SU quadruple, $A = \mathcal{A}(X, \phi, \prec_0, K)$, and let Irrw be the set of irreducible words for $\mathbf{rws}(X, \mathbf{b}, \prec_0)$. Define sets V_n ($n \geq 0$) of overlap chains: words $w = x_r^{n_r} \cdots x_1^{n_1} \in X^*$ with $x_i \succ_0 x_j$ for $i > j$, $n_i > 0$, $\sum n_i = n$, and $n_i > 1$ only if $\phi(x_i, x_i) = 0$.

Theorem 16.1 (Biresolution). *The sequence*

$$(7) \quad 0 \leftarrow A \xleftarrow{\partial_0} A \otimes_K A \xleftarrow{\partial_1} A \otimes_K V_1 K \otimes_K A \leftarrow \cdots$$

is a free (A, A) -bimodule resolution of A , with differential

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_n(1 \otimes x_n \cdots x_1 \otimes 1) &= \sum_{i=1}^n (-1)^{i-1} \phi(x_{i-1} \cdots x_1, x_i) 1 \otimes x_n \cdots \hat{x}_i \cdots x_1 \otimes \bar{x}_i \\ &\quad + \sum_{i=1}^n (-1)^i \phi(x_n \cdots x_{i+1}, x_i) \bar{x}_i \otimes x_n \cdots \hat{x}_i \cdots x_1 \otimes 1, \end{aligned}$$

where $\phi(w, x) = \prod_j \phi(x_j, x)$ over the letters of w . When K is a field the resolution is minimal, and $V_n K \cong \text{Tor}_n^A(K, K)$.

Proof sketch. Exactness follows by constructing contracting homotopies by well-founded induction on the length-lexicographic order on $\hat{V}_n = \{\bar{u} \otimes w \otimes \bar{v} : u, v \in \text{Irrw}, w \in V_n\}$, using completeness of the rewriting system. Minimality when K is a field follows because applying $K \otimes_A -$ yields a complex with zero differential. \square

17. POINCARÉ SERIES AND INVARIANT IDEALS

17.1. The Poincaré series.

Proposition 17.1. *Let $|\mathcal{X}| = m \geq 1$. The Poincaré series of $\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X})$ over a field \mathbb{F} is $P_{\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X})}(t) = (1-t)^{-m}$.*

Proof. The rank formula of [11] gives $|V_n| = \binom{n+m-1}{m-1}$, and summing gives $(1-t)^{-m}$. This depends only on m , not the poset structure. \square

Corollary 17.2. *If \mathbb{F} is a field, then*

$$\mathrm{Tor}_n^{\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, \mathbb{F})}(\mathbb{F}, \mathbb{F}) \cong \mathbb{F}^{\binom{n+m-1}{m-1}}.$$

Proof. By Theorem 16.1, the minimal resolution has

$$\mathrm{Tor}_n^{\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, \mathbb{F})}(\mathbb{F}, \mathbb{F}) \cong V_n \mathbb{F},$$

and Proposition 17.1 gives $\dim_{\mathbb{F}} V_n \mathbb{F} = \binom{n+m-1}{m-1}$. \square

17.2. Invariant ideals.

Theorem 17.3 (Invariant ideals). *The invariant (elementary) ideals of $\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X})$ [7] are*

$$E_{n,i}(\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X})) = \mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X})_{[\vec{\chi}_n - i]}^{\mathrm{ab}},$$

where $\vec{\chi}_n$ is the directed Euler characteristic of the resolution and $\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X})_{[j]}^{\mathrm{ab}}$ is the ideal of $\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X})^{\mathrm{ab}}$ generated by all j -antichains of \mathcal{X} .

Proof. The differential matrices D_n have degree-one entries in A^{ab} . The $p \times p$ submatrix indexed by a p -subset $\{y_1, \dots, y_p\}$ is diagonal with entries $\bar{y}_1, \dots, \bar{y}_p$; its determinant is nonzero in A^{ab} iff $\{y_1, \dots, y_p\}$ is an antichain. The formula follows. \square

Example 17.4. For $\mathcal{X} = \{x_1, x_2, x_3\}$ with $x_1 \prec x_2, x_1 \prec x_3$: antichains are $\emptyset, \{x_1\}, \{x_2\}, \{x_3\}, \{x_2, x_3\}$, width = 2, and

$$E_{n,i}(A) = \begin{cases} 0 & i \leq \vec{\chi}_n - 3, \\ (x_2 x_3) & i = \vec{\chi}_n - 2, \\ A^{\mathrm{ab}+} & i = \vec{\chi}_n - 1, \\ A^{\mathrm{ab}} & i \geq \vec{\chi}_n. \end{cases}$$

18. HOCHSCHILD (CO)HOMOLOGY AND THE EXT ALGEBRA

18.1. The Ext algebra. For a Koszul algebra A_{\bullet} over \mathbb{F} with Koszul dual $A_{\bullet}^!$, $\mathrm{Ext}_A^*(\mathbb{F}, \mathbb{F}) \cong A^!$ [12].

Corollary 18.1. *Let $|\mathcal{X}| = m \geq 1$. The Ext algebra of $\mathbf{AF}_{\bullet}(\mathcal{X}, \mathbb{F})$ is*

$$\mathrm{Ext}_{\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X})}^*(\mathbb{F}, \mathbb{F}) \cong \mathbf{AF}_{\bullet}^!(\mathcal{X}) \cong \mathbb{F}\langle \mathcal{X} ; xy + yx \ (x \not\prec y), \ xy \ (x \prec y) \rangle.$$

In particular, $\mathrm{Ext}_{\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X})}^n(\mathbb{F}, \mathbb{F})$ has rank $\binom{n+m-1}{m-1}$.

Proof. Koszulity (Corollary 12.3) gives $\text{Ext}_{\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X})}^*(\mathbb{F}, \mathbb{F}) \cong \mathbf{AF}_\bullet^!(\mathcal{X})$. The presentation is Proposition 14.4 and the rank is Proposition 17.1. \square

Remark 18.2. When \mathcal{X} is totally ordered, $\mathbf{AF}_\bullet^!(\mathcal{X})$ is the exterior algebra $\bigwedge(\mathcal{X})$, reflecting classical Koszul duality.

18.2. Hochschild homology and cohomology. For a K -algebra A and bimodule M [10]: $\text{HH}_n(A, M) = \text{Tor}_n^{A^e}(A, M)$ and $\text{HH}^n(A, M) = \text{Ext}_{A^e}^n(A, M)$, where $A^e = A \otimes_K A^{\text{op}}$.

Theorem 18.3. *Let $A = \mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, \mathbb{F})$ with $|\mathcal{X}| = m \geq 1$.*

- (i) $\text{HH}_n(A, \mathbb{F}) \cong \mathbb{F}^{\binom{n+m-1}{m-1}}$ for all $n \geq 0$.
- (ii) $\text{HH}^n(A, \mathbb{F}) \cong \mathbb{F}^{\binom{n+m-1}{m-1}}$ for all $n \geq 0$.

The Hochschild Poincaré series with trivial coefficients is $(1-t)^{-m}$.

Proof. Tensor the biresolution with \mathbb{F} over A^e : $P_n \otimes_{A^e} \mathbb{F} \cong V_n \mathbb{F}$, and the induced differential vanishes (each term has a factor in $A_+ = \text{Ker } \varepsilon$ annihilated by ε). So $\text{HH}_n(A, \mathbb{F}) \cong V_n \mathbb{F}$. Dually, $\text{Hom}_{A^e}(P_n, \mathbb{F}) \cong (V_n \mathbb{F})^*$ and coboundaries vanish by minimality, giving $\text{HH}^n(A, \mathbb{F}) \cong (V_n \mathbb{F})^*$. \square

Remark 18.4. The trivial Hochschild (co)homology depends only on $m = |\mathcal{X}|$ and carries no poset information. The invariant ideals of Section 17 provide a strictly finer invariant.

18.3. Hochschild cohomology with coefficients in A . From the biresolution, the cochain complex for $\text{HH}^*(A, A)$ is

$$(8) \quad C^n \cong \text{Hom}_{\mathbb{F}}(V_n \mathbb{F}, A),$$

with coboundary

$$(9) \quad \begin{aligned} (\delta^n \tilde{f})(w) &= \sum_{i=1}^{n+1} (-1)^{i-1} \phi(x_{i-1} \cdots x_1, x_i) \tilde{f}(w_i) \bar{x}_i \\ &+ \sum_{i=1}^{n+1} (-1)^i \phi(x_{n+1} \cdots x_{i+1}, x_i) \bar{x}_i \tilde{f}(w_i) \end{aligned}$$

for $w = x_{n+1} \cdots x_1 \in V_{n+1}$ and w_i the word with x_i omitted. For $\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X})$, $\phi(u, x) = 1$ iff every letter of u is incomparable with x .

The groups $\text{HH}^0(A, A) \cong Z(A)$, $\text{HH}^1(A, A)$ (outer derivations), and $\text{HH}^2(A, A)$ (infinitesimal deformations) have their standard interpretations [8].

Proposition 18.5 (Center of $\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X})$). *$\bar{\sigma} \in Z(\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, \mathbb{F}))$ if and only if for every $x \in \mathcal{X} \setminus \sigma$, at least one of the following holds:*

- (a) x is incomparable with every element of σ ;
- (b) σ contains elements both above and below x , i.e. there exist $y_1, y_2 \in \sigma$ with $y_1 \prec x \prec y_2$.

Proof. $\bar{\sigma} \in Z(A)$ iff $[\bar{\sigma}, \bar{x}] = 0$ for every $x \in \mathcal{X}$. For $x \in \sigma$: both products introduce $\bar{x}^2 = 0$. For $x \notin \sigma$: $\bar{\sigma}\bar{x}$ vanishes iff σ has some $y \succ x$ (relation $\bar{y}\bar{x} = 0$), otherwise equals $\overline{\sigma \cup \{x\}}$; similarly $\bar{x}\bar{\sigma}$ vanishes iff σ has some $y \prec x$. Hence the commutator vanishes precisely in the following two cases: either both products are equal to $\overline{\sigma \cup \{x\}}$, which is equivalent to condition (a), or both products vanish, which is equivalent to condition (b). \square

Corollary 18.6. *If $\mathcal{X} = (\{x_1, \dots, x_m\}, \leq)$ is totally ordered ($m \geq 2$), then*

$$Z(\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X})) = \mathbb{F} \cdot 1 \oplus \bigoplus_{\substack{\sigma \subseteq \mathcal{X} \\ x_1, x_m \in \sigma}} \mathbb{F} \bar{\sigma},$$

of dimension $1 + 2^{m-2}$. If \mathcal{X} is an antichain, $\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X})$ is commutative and $Z(\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X})) = \mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X})$.

Example 18.7. For $\mathcal{X} = (\{x_1, x_2, x_3\}, \leq)$, the center has basis

$$\{1, \bar{x}_1\bar{x}_3, \bar{x}_1\bar{x}_2\bar{x}_3\},$$

so $\dim Z(A) = 3$. For the V poset ($x_1 \prec x_2$, $x_1 \prec x_3$, $x_2 \not\prec x_3$): only \emptyset and \mathcal{X} satisfy both conditions, so $\dim Z(A) = 2$.

Proposition 18.8. *Let $A = \mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, \mathbb{F})$ with $|\mathcal{X}| = m$.*

- (i) $\mathrm{HH}^n(A, A)$ is finite-dimensional for each n .
- (ii) For $n > m$, $\mathrm{HH}^n(A, A)$ is determined by the complex restricted to the diagonal strip $0 \leq p \leq m$.
- (iii) $\mathrm{HH}^*(A, A)$ carries a Gerstenhaber algebra structure: a graded-commutative cup product and a degree -1 Lie bracket.

Remark 18.9 (Deformations of the Butcher group). When \mathcal{X} is totally ordered, $\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X})^{\mathrm{op}}$ is Butcher's algebra (Proposition 3.10) and $\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X})^\times$ is the Butcher group. The space $\mathrm{HH}^2(A, A)$ parametrizes its infinitesimal deformations, while the Gerstenhaber bracket $[-, -]: \mathrm{HH}^2 \otimes \mathrm{HH}^2 \rightarrow \mathrm{HH}^3$ controls obstructions. By Corollary 18.6, $\dim Z(A) = 1 + 2^{m-2}$ for $m \geq 2$: despite being highly noncommutative, the Butcher algebra has a center growing exponentially with m .

19. HOPF ALGEBRAS OF FILTERS

19.1. Transitivity of ideals.

Lemma 19.1. *Let $\sigma \subseteq \mathcal{X}$.*

- (i) *If $J \in \mathcal{I}(I)$ and $I \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma)$, then $J \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma)$.*
- (ii) *If $I \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma)$ and $J \in \mathcal{I}(I)$, then $I \setminus J \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma \setminus J)$.*
- (iii) *If $I \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma)$ and $L \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma \setminus I)$, then $I \cup L \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma)$ and $I \in \mathcal{I}(I \cup L)$.*

Proof. (i) Take $x \in J$ and $y \in \sigma$ with $y \preceq x$. Since $x \in J \subseteq I$ and $I \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma)$, we have $y \in I$. Then $J \in \mathcal{I}(I)$ implies $y \in J$.

(ii) Let $x \in I \setminus J$ and $y \in \sigma \setminus J$ with $y \preceq x$. Since $x \in I$ and $I \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma)$, we have $y \in I$. Because $y \notin J$, it follows that $y \in I \setminus J$.

(iii) Let $x \in I \cup L$ and $y \in \sigma$ with $y \preceq x$. If $x \in I$, then $y \in I \subseteq I \cup L$ because $I \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma)$. If $x \in L \subseteq \sigma \setminus I$, then either $y \in I$, hence $y \in I \cup L$, or $y \in \sigma \setminus I$, in which case $L \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma \setminus I)$ gives $y \in L$. For the second statement, if $x \in I$ and $y \in I \cup L$ satisfy $y \preceq x$, then $I \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma)$ gives $y \in I$. \square

19.2. Definition and basic Hopf structure.

Definition 19.2. Let (\mathcal{X}, \preceq) be a finite poset. The *Hopf algebra of filters* $\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ is the commutative polynomial algebra

$$\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{X}, K) = K[y_\sigma : \sigma \in 2^{\mathcal{X}} \setminus \{\emptyset\}],$$

equipped with:

- (i) grading $\deg(y_\sigma) = |\sigma|$, extended multiplicatively;
- (ii) coproduct

$$(10) \quad \Delta(y_\sigma) = \sum_{I \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma)} y_{\sigma \setminus I} \otimes y_I,$$

where $y_\emptyset = 1$;

- (iii) counit determined by $\varepsilon(y_\sigma) = 0$ for $\sigma \neq \emptyset$.

Remark 19.3. The coproduct (10) can be written as

$$\Delta(y_\sigma) = y_\sigma \otimes 1 + 1 \otimes y_\sigma + \sum_{\substack{I \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma) \\ \emptyset \subsetneq I \subsetneq \sigma}} y_{\sigma \setminus I} \otimes y_I.$$

The first tensor factor records the filter part and the second the ideal part, matching the Connes–Kreimer convention of pruned part \otimes trunk.

Theorem 19.4. *The triple $(\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{X}, K), \Delta, \varepsilon)$ is a graded connected commutative bialgebra. In particular, it admits a unique antipode S and is therefore a Hopf algebra.*

Proof. Since $\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ is a polynomial algebra, it is enough to check coassociativity and the counit axiom on the generators.

For coassociativity, compute

$$\begin{aligned} (\Delta \otimes \text{id})\Delta(y_\sigma) &= \sum_{I \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma)} \sum_{L \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma \setminus I)} y_{(\sigma \setminus I) \setminus L} \otimes y_L \otimes y_I, \\ (\text{id} \otimes \Delta)\Delta(y_\sigma) &= \sum_{I' \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma)} \sum_{J \in \mathcal{I}(I')} y_{\sigma \setminus I'} \otimes y_{I' \setminus J} \otimes y_J. \end{aligned}$$

The change of variables $(I, L) \mapsto (I' = I \cup L, J = I)$ is well-defined by Lemma 19.1(iii), and its inverse $(I', J) \mapsto (I = J, L = I' \setminus J)$ is well-defined by Lemma 19.1(i)–(ii). Under this bijection the summands coincide, so Δ is coassociative.

For the counit, only the terms $I = \emptyset$ and $I = \sigma$ survive:

$$(\text{id} \otimes \varepsilon)\Delta(y_\sigma) = y_\sigma, \quad (\varepsilon \otimes \text{id})\Delta(y_\sigma) = y_\sigma.$$

Thus $(\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{X}, K), \Delta, \varepsilon)$ is a graded connected commutative bialgebra. The existence and uniqueness of the antipode then follow from the standard theorem for graded connected bialgebras; see Takeuchi [17]. \square

Proposition 19.5. *The antipode is determined recursively on generators by*

$$(11) \quad S(y_\sigma) = -y_\sigma - \sum_{\substack{I \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma) \\ \emptyset \subsetneq I \subsetneq \sigma}} S(y_{\sigma \setminus I}) y_I$$

for each $\sigma \neq \emptyset$.

Proof. For $\sigma \neq \emptyset$, the identity $\mu(S \otimes \text{id})\Delta(y_\sigma) = \varepsilon(y_\sigma) = 0$ becomes

$$\sum_{I \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma)} S(y_{\sigma \setminus I}) y_I = 0.$$

Separating the terms $I = \emptyset$ and $I = \sigma$ yields (11). Since $|\sigma \setminus I| < |\sigma|$ for $I \neq \emptyset$, the recursion is well-founded. \square

20. CHARACTERS, CONNECTED QUOTIENTS, AND FUNCTORIALITY

20.1. Characters and the augmentation-one unit group. A character of $\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ is a K -algebra homomorphism $\varphi: \mathcal{H}(\mathcal{X}, K) \rightarrow K$. The set $G(\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{X}), K)$ of characters is a group under convolution:

$$(\varphi \star \psi)(h) = \mu_K(\varphi \otimes \psi)\Delta(h).$$

Theorem 20.1. *There is a group isomorphism*

$$G(\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{X}), K) \xrightarrow{\sim} \text{SL}(\mathcal{X}, K)^{\text{op}}.$$

Proof. Given a character φ , define $f_\varphi \in \mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ by $f_\varphi(\emptyset) = 1$ and $f_\varphi(\sigma) = \varphi(y_\sigma)$ for $\sigma \neq \emptyset$. This gives a bijection between characters and elements of $\text{SL}(\mathcal{X}, K)$.

For $\sigma \neq \emptyset$,

$$\begin{aligned} (\varphi \star \psi)(y_\sigma) &= \sum_{I \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma)} \varphi(y_{\sigma \setminus I}) \psi(y_I) \\ &= \sum_{I \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma)} f_\varphi(\sigma \setminus I) f_\psi(I). \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand,

$$(f_\psi \star f_\varphi)(\sigma) = \sum_{I \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma)} f_\psi(I) f_\varphi(\sigma \setminus I).$$

Hence $f_{\varphi \star \psi} = f_\psi \star f_\varphi$, so convolution of characters corresponds to the opposite of multiplication in $\text{SL}(\mathcal{X}, K)$. \square

20.2. Connected quotients and the Connes–Kreimer coproduct.

Definition 20.2. A nonempty subset $\sigma \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ is *connected* if its comparability graph is connected. We write $\text{Conn}(\mathcal{X})$ for the set of nonempty connected subsets of \mathcal{X} .

Every nonempty subset $\sigma \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ has a unique decomposition $\sigma = C_1 \sqcup \cdots \sqcup C_k$ into connected components, and different components are pairwise incomparable.

Lemma 20.3. *If $\sigma = C_1 \sqcup \cdots \sqcup C_k$ is the connected-component decomposition of σ , then*

$$\mathcal{I}(\sigma) = \mathcal{I}(C_1) \times \cdots \times \mathcal{I}(C_k).$$

Proof. Because distinct components are pairwise incomparable, the ideal condition on a subset of σ can be checked independently on each component. \square

For $\sigma \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ with connected components C_1, \dots, C_k , define

$$\tilde{z}_\sigma = z_{C_1} \cdots z_{C_k} \in K[z_C : C \in \text{Conn}(\mathcal{X})], \quad \tilde{z}_\emptyset = 1.$$

Definition 20.4. The *connected quotient* $\mathcal{H}^c(\mathcal{X}, K)$ is the polynomial algebra $K[z_C : C \in \text{Conn}(\mathcal{X})]$, graded by $\deg(z_C) = |C|$, with coproduct

$$(12) \quad \Delta^c(z_C) = \sum_{I \in \mathcal{I}(C)} \tilde{z}_{C \setminus I} \otimes \tilde{z}_I$$

for $C \in \text{Conn}(\mathcal{X})$, extended as an algebra homomorphism.

Proposition 20.5. *The surjection $\pi: \mathcal{H}(\mathcal{X}, K) \twoheadrightarrow \mathcal{H}^c(\mathcal{X}, K)$ defined by $\pi(y_\sigma) = \tilde{z}_\sigma$ is a Hopf algebra homomorphism. In particular, $\mathcal{H}^c(\mathcal{X}, K)$ is a graded connected commutative Hopf algebra.*

Proof. Let $\sigma = C_1 \sqcup \cdots \sqcup C_k$ be the connected-component decomposition. Using Lemma 20.3,

$$\begin{aligned} (\pi \otimes \pi)\Delta(y_\sigma) &= \sum_{I_1 \in \mathcal{I}(C_1)} \cdots \sum_{I_k \in \mathcal{I}(C_k)} \tilde{z}_{(C_1 \setminus I_1) \sqcup \cdots \sqcup (C_k \setminus I_k)} \otimes \tilde{z}_{I_1 \sqcup \cdots \sqcup I_k} \\ &= \prod_{j=1}^k \left(\sum_{I_j \in \mathcal{I}(C_j)} \tilde{z}_{C_j \setminus I_j} \otimes \tilde{z}_{I_j} \right) \\ &= \prod_{j=1}^k \Delta^c(z_{C_j}) = \Delta^c \left(\prod_{j=1}^k z_{C_j} \right) = \Delta^c(\pi(y_\sigma)). \end{aligned}$$

Thus $(\pi \otimes \pi)\Delta = \Delta^c \pi$ on generators, hence on all of $\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{X}, K)$. Counit compatibility is immediate. \square

Theorem 20.6. *Let (\mathcal{X}, \preceq) be a finite rooted forest with the tree ordering, each root minimal in its component. Then the coproduct (12) on $\mathcal{H}^c(\mathcal{X}, K)$ is the labeled Connes–Kreimer coproduct: ideals are precisely rooted subtrees containing the root, and complements decompose into the pruned forest.*

Proof. For a connected subset C of a rooted forest, the ideals of C are exactly the downward-closed subtrees containing the root of C . If $I \in \mathcal{I}(C)$, then $C \setminus I$ is an upper set, hence a disjoint union of rooted subtrees. Therefore the term $\tilde{z}_{C \setminus I} \otimes \tilde{z}_I$ records precisely the pruned forest and the trunk, exactly as in the Connes–Kreimer coproduct. \square

20.3. Functoriality.

Definition 20.7. Let **FinPos** denote the category whose objects are finite posets and whose morphisms are order embeddings.

Theorem 20.8. *The assignment $(\mathcal{X}, \preceq) \mapsto \mathcal{H}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ extends to a covariant functor*

$$\mathcal{H}(-, K): \mathbf{FinPos} \longrightarrow \mathbf{HopfAlg}_K$$

by sending an order embedding $f: \mathcal{X} \hookrightarrow \mathcal{Y}$ to the unique algebra homomorphism determined by

$$(13) \quad \mathcal{H}(f)(y_\sigma) = y_{f(\sigma)}, \quad \emptyset \neq \sigma \subseteq \mathcal{X}.$$

Proof. Because f is injective, $f(\sigma)$ is nonempty whenever σ is. So the formula defines an algebra map on generators.

To check compatibility with the coproduct, note that $I \mapsto f(I)$ is a bijection $\mathcal{I}_\mathcal{X}(\sigma) \rightarrow \mathcal{I}_\mathcal{Y}(f(\sigma))$: this follows directly from the defining property of an order embedding. Using also $f(\sigma \setminus I) = f(\sigma) \setminus f(I)$,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_\mathcal{Y}(\mathcal{H}(f)(y_\sigma)) &= \sum_{J \in \mathcal{I}_\mathcal{Y}(f(\sigma))} y_{f(\sigma) \setminus J} \otimes y_J \\ &= \sum_{I \in \mathcal{I}_\mathcal{X}(\sigma)} y_{f(\sigma \setminus I)} \otimes y_{f(I)} \\ &= (\mathcal{H}(f) \otimes \mathcal{H}(f)) \left(\sum_{I \in \mathcal{I}_\mathcal{X}(\sigma)} y_{\sigma \setminus I} \otimes y_I \right) \\ &= (\mathcal{H}(f) \otimes \mathcal{H}(f)) \Delta_\mathcal{X}(y_\sigma). \end{aligned}$$

Counit compatibility and functoriality are immediate on generators. \square

Corollary 20.9. *There is a contravariant functor*

$$G(\mathcal{H}(-), K): \mathbf{FinPos}^{\text{op}} \longrightarrow \mathbf{Grp}$$

which sends \mathcal{X} to $G(\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{X}), K) \cong \text{SL}(\mathcal{X}, K)^{\text{op}}$.

Proof. Precomposition with a Hopf algebra map sends characters to characters and reverses composition. The identification with $\text{SL}(\mathcal{X}, K)^{\text{op}}$ is Theorem 20.1. \square

21. PRIMITIVE ELEMENTS AND COCOMMUTATIVITY

Proposition 21.1. *The primitive elements of $\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ are precisely the generators $y_{\{x\}}$ for $x \in \mathcal{X}$:*

$$\text{Prim}(\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{X}, K)) = \bigoplus_{x \in \mathcal{X}} K y_{\{x\}}.$$

Proof. An element y_σ is primitive if and only if $\Delta(y_\sigma) = y_\sigma \otimes 1 + 1 \otimes y_\sigma$, which is equivalent to $\mathcal{I}(\sigma) = \{\emptyset, \sigma\}$. This holds for singleton subsets. If $|\sigma| \geq 2$, choose a minimal element x of (σ, \preceq) ; then $\{x\}$ is a proper nontrivial ideal of σ , so y_σ is not primitive. \square

Proposition 21.2. *The Hopf algebra $\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ is cocommutative if and only if \mathcal{X} is an antichain.*

Proof. The coproduct is cocommutative if and only if

$$\sum_{I \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma)} y_{\sigma \setminus I} \otimes y_I = \sum_{I \in \mathcal{I}(\sigma)} y_I \otimes y_{\sigma \setminus I}$$

for every $\sigma \subseteq \mathcal{X}$. This is equivalent to $\mathcal{I}(\sigma) = \mathcal{F}(\sigma)$ for every σ , hence to the condition that every subset is both an ideal and a filter. That happens exactly when \mathcal{X} is an antichain. \square

22. CONCLUDING REMARKS

We have developed a unified theory of the algebra of filters and their associated Hopf-algebraic structures.

Part I. The embedding $\varphi: \mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, K) \hookrightarrow \mathbf{IA}(2^{\mathcal{X}}, \subseteq)$ places our algebra within Rota's classical framework, and the connection to Butcher's algebra shows that $\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ generalizes a fundamental object in numerical analysis and renormalization. The isomorphism with unitary convolution (Theorem 5.5) provides a new algebraic perspective on multiplicative number theory.

Part II. The group of units is always nilpotent of class at most $|\mathcal{X}|$, admits unique factorization, and is polycyclic exactly when $(K, +)$ is finitely generated. When \mathcal{X} is a chain of length m , $\text{SL}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ embeds into the group of upper unitriangular $(m+1) \times (m+1)$ matrices.

Part III. Koszulity and the minimal biresolution give a detailed homological picture. The trivial Hochschild (co)homology depends only on $|\mathcal{X}|$, while the invariant ideals and the center $Z(\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}))$ detect finer poset structure.

Part IV. The Hopf algebra $\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ packages the same ideal-decomposition data coalgebraically. Its character group recovers $\text{SL}(\mathcal{X}, K)^{\text{op}}$. The connected quotient $\mathcal{H}^c(\mathcal{X}, K)$ recovers the Connes–Kreimer coproduct for rooted forests, and functoriality with respect to order embeddings places this construction in a categorical framework.

We close with open questions:

- (1) What is the Möbius function of $\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ viewed through the embedding into $\mathbf{IA}(2^{\mathcal{X}}, \subseteq)$?
- (2) How do the Hopf algebras $\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{X}, K)$ and $\mathcal{H}^c(\mathcal{X}, K)$ relate functorially to Schmitt's incidence Hopf algebras [14]?
- (3) Compute $\mathrm{HH}^n(\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}), \mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X}))$ for $n \geq 1$ explicitly in terms of the combinatorics of \mathcal{X} , and determine the Gerstenhaber algebra structure.
- (4) Develop Birkhoff factorization and renormalization-type constructions on the character group $G(\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{X}), K) \cong \mathrm{SL}(\mathcal{X}, K)^{\mathrm{op}}$, in the spirit of Connes–Kreimer [6].
- (5) Investigate the global dimension of $\mathbf{AF}(\mathcal{X})$ for infinite posets.

REFERENCES

- [1] David J. Anick, *On the homology of associative algebras*, Trans. Amer. Math. Soc. **296** (1986), 641–659.
- [2] George M. Bergman, *The diamond lemma for ring theory*, Adv. Math. **29** (1978), 178–218.
- [3] John C. Butcher, *An algebraic theory of integration methods*, Math. Comp. **26** (1972), 79–106.
- [4] Eckford Cohen, *Arithmetical functions associated with the unitary divisors of an integer*, Math. Z. **74** (1960), 66–80.
- [5] Alain Connes and Dirk Kreimer, *Hopf algebras, renormalization and noncommutative geometry*, Comm. Math. Phys. **199** (1998), 203–242.
- [6] ———, *Renormalization in quantum field theory and the Riemann–Hilbert problem. I. The Hopf algebra structure of graphs and the main theorem*, Comm. Math. Phys. **210** (2000), 249–273.
- [7] Ralph H. Fox, *Free differential calculus. I. Derivation in the free group ring*, Ann. of Math. (2) **57** (1953), 547–560.
- [8] Murray Gerstenhaber, *On the deformation of rings and algebras*, Ann. of Math. (2) **79** (1964), 59–103.
- [9] Philip Hall, *The Edmonton notes on nilpotent groups*, Queen Mary College Mathematics Notes, Queen Mary College, London, 1969.
- [10] Jean-Louis Loday, *Cyclic homology*, 2nd ed., Grundlehren der Mathematischen Wissenschaften, vol. 301, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1998.
- [11] Alexandro Olivares-Acosta, *Koszul algebras from combinatorics, and their products and invariant ideals*, Ph.D. thesis, University of Glasgow, 2005.
- [12] Alexander Polishchuk and Leonid Positselski, *Quadratic algebras*, University Lecture Series, vol. 37, Amer. Math. Soc., Providence, RI, 2005.
- [13] Gian-Carlo Rota, *On the foundations of combinatorial theory. I. Theory of Möbius functions*, Z. Wahrscheinlichkeitstheorie und Verw. Gebiete **2** (1964), 340–368.
- [14] William R. Schmitt, *Incidence Hopf algebras*, J. Pure Appl. Algebra **96** (1994), 299–330.
- [15] Daniel Segal, *Polycyclic groups*, Cambridge Tracts in Mathematics, vol. 82, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1983.
- [16] Richard P. Stanley, *Combinatorics and commutative algebra*, 2nd ed., Progress in Mathematics, vol. 41, Birkhäuser, Boston, MA, 1996.
- [17] Mitsuhiro Takeuchi, *Free Hopf algebras generated by coalgebras*, J. Math. Soc. Japan **23** (1971), 561–582.
- [18] Ramaswamy Vaidyanathaswamy, *The theory of multiplicative arithmetic functions*, Trans. Amer. Math. Soc. **33** (1931), 579–662.

Email address: `aoa@ugd.edu.mx`

UNIVERSIDAD GESTALT DE DISEÑO, MEXICO